

Ultra Wideband Pulse Modulation System in Comparison to Conventional Narrowband Wireless Systems

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Abstract—Ultra-Wideband (UWB) technology is a wireless transmission scheme that occupies a bandwidth of more than 25% of a center frequency, or more than 1.5GHz. It uses very narrow band pulses of nano-seconds duration to provide very high data rate communications. These pulses spread the energy over a large frequency range because of which it is called ultra-wideband. Ultra wideband (UWB) technology, useful for both communication and remote sensing applications. In this paper, we will discuss the UWB pulse modulation system using gaussian pulse its advantages and comparison with conventional narrowband wireless systems.

Keywords: UWB, PPM, WUSB, PAM.

Introduction

UWB transmission is a signal that occupies a bandwidth of greater than 500 MHz as compared to conventional narrowband systems. Due to the very short duration of the pulses, the UWB signal's spectrum can be several gigahertz's wide. UWB technology has a wide variety of WPAN applications like replacing of cables between portable multimedia devices, enabling high-speed wireless universal serial bus (WUSB) connectivity for personal computers (PC) and peripherals, creating ad-hoc high-bit-rate wireless connectivity PC and mobile devices.

The common pulse shape for UWB communication system is the Gaussian pulse and its derivatives due to ease of generation. The Gaussian pulse is defined as

$$p(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(t-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad -\infty < t < \infty \quad (1)$$

Where σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian pulse, and μ is the location in time for the midpoint of the gaussian pulse in seconds[4] [5].

Modulation

UWB can directly modulate impulse pulses of nano-seconds duration that results in a waveform that occupies several GHz of bandwidth[3].

Fig.2.UWB impulse modulation

UWB signals are obtained by either applying the Pulse Position (PPM), Pulse Amplitude (PAM), Bi-Phase modulation

A. PPM Modulation

In PPM modulation, each pulse is sent in advance or delayed to a regular time scale. A binary communication system can be established with a forward or backward shift of the pulse in time. The data is encoded by adding an extra time shift “ δ shift” to the impulse as shown in the Fig2

B. PAM Modulation

The second data modulation scheme is pulse amplitude modulation (PAM), which is based on encoding the data in the amplitude of the impulses. Fig.3. shows a PAM modulated signal.

C. Bi-phase modulation (BPM)

In Bi-phase modulation (BPM) we invert the pulse, to create a pulse having opposite phase. This is known as. Bi-phase is therefore antipodal as shown in Fig.4.

Fig.2. PPM Modulation

Fig.3. PAM Modulation

Fig.4. Bi-phase Modulation

Comparison with Existing Wireless Standards

Currently, the following conventional wireless standards, i.e., Bluetooth, IEEE802.11a, IEEE802.11b, and IEEE802.11g are commonly used.

A. 802.11a

IT works on OFDM technology. Its frequency spectrum occupies 300 MHz in three different bandwidths of 100 MHz each. lower band (5.150 to 5.250 GHz), UNII middle band (5.250 to 5.350 GHz), UNII upper band (5.725 to 5.825 GHz). 802.11a provides 12 channels of 20 MHz each and can offer data rate up to 54 MHz. has a range of about 20 meters in free space and spatial capacity of approximately 515 Kbps/m².

B. 802.11b

It employs direct sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) with complementary code keying (CCK) base-band modulation. Its RF spectrum occupies 83.5 MHz bandwidth from 2.4 GHz to 2.4835 GHz. 802.11b has 11 channels, each of which is 22 MHz wide, and offers data speeds up to 11Mbps. It has a range of about 100 meters and spatial capacity of approximately 1 Kbps/m²

C. 802.11g

It offers data speeds up to 54Mbps, and operates at radio frequency between 2.4 GHz and 2.4835 GHz. 802.11g uses 802.11b's Complementary Code Keying (CCK) to achieve bit transfer rates of 11Mbps. In addition, it adopts 802.11a's Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) modulation for data rate of 54Mbps. It has a range of about 50 meters and spatial capacity of approximately 83 Kbps/m²

D. Bluetooth

Bluetooth, also known as the IEEE 802.15.1 standard is based on a wireless radio system designed for short-range and cheap devices to replace cables for computer peripherals, such as mice, keyboards, joysticks, and printers. A contemporary example of a low-cost, short-range wireless architecture is the Bluetooth radio, an example of which is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Bluetooth transceiver

Bluetooth uses a form of Frequency Shift Keying (FSK) where information is sent by shifting the carrier frequency high or low. The information bits applied to a Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO). A synthesizer with a crystal reference oscillator is required to keep this oscillator's average frequency within specific limits. This 1MHz-wide signal is then spread to 79MHz by a frequency-hopping technique where the synthesizer is tuned to pseudo random channels spaced at 1MHz. The resulting emitted signal is centered at 2.45GHz with a bandwidth of 79MHz.

In receive mode, the signal from the antenna is first amplified and then down-converted to an Intermediate Frequency (IF). The down-converter uses a heterodyne technique where a non-linear “mixer” is fed both the desired signal at ~2.45GHz and a synthesized local oscillator. The mixer produces a plethora of images of the desired signal where each image is centered at the sum and difference terms of the desired signal and the local oscillator. The signal that falls at the desired IF frequency then passes through the IF filter, while the other signals are rejected.

Bluetooth, in its low-power mode, has a rated 10-meter range and a peak over-the-air speed of 1Mbps.

UWB Transceiver

This transceiver could be used for the same applications targeted for use with Bluetooth, but at higher data rates and lower emitted Radio Frequency (RF) power. The information could be modulated using several different techniques like Pulse Position, Pulse amplitude, Bi phase etc. The pulse has duration on the order of nano seconds and its shape is designed to concentrate energy over the broad range of 3-6GHz. A power amplifier may not be required in this case because the pulse generator need only produce a voltage swing on the order of 100mV.

In receive mode, the energy collected by the antenna is amplified and passed through either a matched filter or a correlation-type receiver. A matched filter has an impulse response matched to the received pulse shape and will produce an impulse at its output when presented with RF energy which has the correct (matching) pulse shape. The original information is then recovered with an adjustable high-gain threshold circuit.

So we can see that, It has no reference oscillator, no synthesizer, no VCO and no need of carrier frequency adjustment. Thus UWB systems vary widely in their projected capabilities, but one UWB technology developer has measured peak speeds of over 480 Mbps at a range of 10 meters with spatial capacity of approximately 10000 Kbps/m²

Some key characteristics of existing wireless standards and UWB technology are summarized below in Table 1.

Table1. Key characteristics of existing wireless standards and UWB technology

Technology	Operating range	Peek speed	Modulation	Frequency Band	Capacityin bits/sec/sqm
IEEE802.11b	100 m	11Mbps	DSSS	2.4 GHz	1 Kbps/m ²
IEEE802.11g	50 m	54 Mbps	OFDM	2.4 GHz	83 Kbps/m ² .
IEEE802.11a	20 m	54 Mbps	OFDM	5 GHz	515 Kbps/m ² .
Bluetooth	10 m	1Mbps	FHSS	2.4 GHz	30 Kbps/m ² .
UWB	10 m	480 Mbps	Multi-band OFDM	3-10GHz	1,0000 kbps/m ²

Advantages of the UWB

- I. **Power Consumption:-** UWB radio offers short-range communication that uses 1/1000 of the power required for equivalent conventional transmission methods.
- II. **High Security:-** Because of their low average transmission power, UWB communications systems have an inherent immunity to detection and interception.

- III. **High Performance in Multipath Channels:-** The phenomenon known as multipath interference is unavoidable in many wireless communications channels. When signals are transmitted between transmitter and receiver, they scatter, reflected from objects and surfaces along the path. At the receiver end, the receiver sees the superposition of delayed versions of the original signal. When signals are continuous-waves or sinusoidal waveforms, these ‘replicas’ may cancel the original signal due to the phase difference of the signals. UWB communication uses pulse waveforms and they tend not to overlap in time because of the extreme narrowness of the pulse.
- IV. **Resistance to Interference** Because of their low power spectrum density, unlicensed UWB radios will cause no interference to other radio systems operating in dedicated bands.
- V. Allows spectrum reuse
- VI. It has immunity to multipath and interference
- VII. **High-speed:-**UWB signals have the capability to convey high-speed data. It has wide frequency bandwidth, it is inherently suited for high data rate communications. For instance the data rate of the IEEE 802.15.3a UWB proposals can achieve up to 480Mbps. This is a giant leap from the existing 1 Mbps of Bluetooth, 11 Mbps of 802.11b, and 54 Mbps of 802.11a/g.

Conclusion

In this paper UWB modulation system and comparison with conventional narrowband wireless systems are explained along with the advantages of ultra wideband system compared to other wireless systems . From above it is concluded that UWB system has peak speeds of over 480 Mbps at a range of 10 meters with very less power consumption as compared to bluetooth standard which operates with in the same 10 m range. Also UWB systems have better spatial efficiency over all other existing wireless standards. Since the average power consumption of a UWB transmitter grows linearly with Pulse Repetition Frequency (PRF), it is easy to envision a relatively simple UWB radio that, under software control, can dynamically trade data rate, power consumption, and range. This type of flexibility is what is needed to enable the power constrained portable computing applications of the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Z. Win and R. A. Scholtz, “Ultra-wide bandwidth time-hopping spread-spectrum impulse radio for wireless multiple-access communication”. IEEE Transactions Volume: 52, Issue: 10, Oct. 2004, pp. 1786- 1796.
- [2] Federal Communications Commission, “Revision of Part 15 of the commission’s rules regarding ultra-wideband transmission systems, FIRST REPORT AND ORDER,” *ET Docket 98-153, FCC 02-48*, pp. 1–118, February 14, 2002.
- [3] Goyal, Vikas, and B. S. Dhaliwal. "ULTRA WIDEBAND PULSE GENERATION USING MULTIPLE ACCESS MODULATION SCHEMES." *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*, ISSN: 2277-9655 , IJESRT4(5), pp. 53-59, May 2015
- [4] Goyal, Vikas. "PULSE GENERATION AND ANALYSIS OF ULTRA WIDE BAND SYSTEM MODEL." *Computer Science & Telecommunication* 2, no. 34: 3-6.
- [5] Goyal, Vikas, and B. S. Dhaliwal. "Optimal Pulse Generation for the improvement of ultra wideband system performance." *Engineering and Computational Sciences (RAECS), 2014 Recent Advances in*. IEEE, 2014.
- [6] Goyal, Vikas, and B. S. Dhaliwal. "Analysis of UWB Multiple Access Modulation Scheme using Pulse Position Modulation." *Computer Science & Telecommunications* 45.1 (2015).
- [7] Goyal, Vikas, and B. S. Dhaliwal. "Ultra Wideband PAM Modulation and Reception in UWB Multi Path channel Using Rake Configurations." *Computer Science & Telecommunications* 45.1 (2015).
- [8] Goyal, Vikas, and B. S. Dhaliwal. " Analyzing Pulse Position Modulation Time Hopping UWB in IEEE UWB Channel." *Computer Science & Telecommunications* 46.2 (2015).
- [9] R. Saadane, A. Khafaji, M. Wahbi, B. El Bhiri, D. Aboutajdine, “Ultra wide bandwidth radio channel indoor propagation and path loss analysis based on measurements,” *Conf. Multimedia Computing and Systems*, pp. 259-263, 2009
- [10] J. G. Proakis, *Digital Communications*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 5th ed., 2001.
- [11] T. Rappaport, “Wireless Communications Principles and Practice”, Pearson Education, 2nd ed., 2004.